

A Quest For Clean Energy

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ABSTRACT

Electricity is taken for granted, everyone is constantly on phones and electronic devices, and is in the use of a multitude of modern electric devices. However, there is often little consideration given to the actual effort required to generate that electricity. One might think that the power of their body would easily be enough to keep their phone powered. However, using a bicycle-powered generator would take hours to charge a phone, resulting in a small percentage. A significant amount of effort is required to generate even a small amount of electricity. When we rely on non-renewable sources, such as natural gas and coal, as the primary sources of electricity, it quickly generates a large amount of greenhouse gas emissions. In fact, electricity produces 25% percent of the United States' emissions. Therefore, a clean source of energy should be prioritized. The primary low-carbon energy sources are hydroelectric, wind, solar, and nuclear. Hydroelectric still produces a sizable amount of greenhouse gas, as well as severely damaging local wildlife, so resources shouldn't be focused on it. Wind and solar energy sources don't produce any emissions in operation and have a minimal impact on local wildlife, but they are inefficient. Nuclear, however, is very efficient, producing no emissions in operation and having a minimal impact on local wildlife, in addition to being much safer than commonly thought. Therefore, nuclear energy is the energy source that should be focused on.

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CHAPTER 1

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Introduction

The research for this project is divided into two separate sections. First is pre-experiment research, in order to justify and inform the experiment I will complete. The second portion involves answering a research question raised by the experiment's conclusion.

Pre-experiment Research

Initially, the idea was that it would be possible to power a battery with a bicycle, making it a viable and clean source of energy for personal use. According to *Pedal Power! How to Build a Bike Generator*: Building a bicycle power generator involves attaching the back wheel of the bike to a motor and connecting the motor to a battery, ensuring the use of a diode (Arndt & Laughlin, 2014). A diode is important to use because it utilizes its built-in electric field to direct the electric flow in only one direction (Granath, 2020), which converts AC current into DC current. AC current flows in both directions, whereas DC current flows in only one direction. It is possible to build a bicycle generator if it is made stationary, by lifting the back wheel (Opez, n.d.). But sentiment is turning in favor of going out bicycling (Strauss, 2021), so if a mobile bicycle

generator were possible, it would be more helpful. However, according to information from the same source, much of current bicycle use is recreational. Therefore, while a stationary bicycle generator is not optimal, it makes sense to use it. Thus, from there the first step was to build a stationary bicycle generator. And the question for the experiment would be, is bicycle energy a viable way to reduce energy in your home? And then, I will try to use that to create a mobile version that can power a laptop without too much battery usage. I thought a laptop is a good goal because we use them a lot and they use energy, but they use a relatively small amount of energy (*How Many Watts Does A Laptop Use?*, 2022) compared to other appliances we may use.

Experiment Conclusion

The question for the experiment project was, can bicycle energy be used as a viable way to generate energy on a regular basis? The short answer to that question is no. At a rate of 20 minutes a day it would take a week to get the power bank to five percent. This makes regular use not feasible or practical. This shows the importance of clean energy though, because this experiment shows that even a small device takes a lot of energy, and people use many devices throughout their days. And the experiment shows that it really takes a lot to make electricity.

Post-experiment Research

Introduction to Research project

What is the best source of energy to focus resources on, in terms of the energy sources' emissions and efficiency? That is the question this research is meant to answer. But first, why is this an important question? As concluded from the experiment, people on their own cannot produce the amount of energy they use, and this is important because of the amount of greenhouse gas emissions caused by making electricity. Electricity produces a quarter of U.S. total greenhouse gas emissions, making it the second largest greenhouse gas producing economic sector (EPA, 2015). And so, given electricity is such a large producer of emissions, and generating electricity is difficult, finding a clean and efficient source of energy is an important task. This will be done by researching the top low-carbon energy sources, which are hydroelectric, wind, solar, and nuclear power (Nyberg, n.d.).

Hydroelectric power

According to an article from Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT) climate portal, Worldwide, hydropower is the largest “low-carbon energy source,” producing nearly eight times more than solar power (Fendt & Parsons, 2021). The source goes on to say, “Hydro plants need a consistent supply of water and a large amount of land” meaning that there is a limited amount of locations for a hydropower dam. And, the building of a dam can cause problems because a dam requires a large reservoir, and

creating that reservoir floods out plants and other organic matter. And “This material decays over time, releasing greenhouse gasses” (Fendt & Parsons, 2021) and this greenhouse gas emissions is highly variable, so hydropower, on average, produces much more greenhouse gas emissions than other low-carbon sources. And According to Fendt & Parsons most developed countries, including the U.S. “have already built out most of their suitable hydro resources” meaning that there isn’t a whole lot of growing potential for the hydroelectric power industry. And finally, “Reservoirs drastically change the landscape and rivers they are built on” (Fendt & Parsons, 2021) and this change of landscape negatively impacts wildlife around the dam, and have forced humans to relocate as well.

Wind Power

The Article *Wind energy facts, advantages, and disadvantages* by John Dabiri says that wind energy is a “small but fast-growing fraction of electricity production.” The growth of wind energy means that the price of wind energy has been decreasing (Dabiri, n.d.). This is important information because growth potential plays a large part in the viability of focusing resources in a power source. This makes wind already have an edge over hydroelectric power, because there isn’t much growth happening in hydropower. Wind power doesn't have the growth issues that hydroelectric dams have though, it still has other drawbacks that must be considered. One important factor to consider is the reliability, wind power requires wind in order to work, and extreme winds can cause

problems with that, because “a strong gale contains 1,000 times more power than a light breeze” (Dabiri, n.d.), this wide range of wind strength is a problem, as wind turbines have not been able to capture this wide range of input. And according to Dabiri, “turbines may be overbuilt to withstand winds they will not experience at many sites, driving up costs and material use.” But, if wind turbines aren’t overbuilt they run the risk of underbuilding them, which would cause much worse problems. Wind power doesn’t produce any greenhouse gasses while operating but, “The construction and maintenance of wind farms involves energy-intensive activities such as trucking, road-building, concrete production, and steel construction” (Dabiri, n.d.). Any power source requires Construction and maintenance, but because of the size of turbines there is an extra large amount of trucking needed for wind turbines to be made. And the final thing that needs to be mentioned is that wind farms affect wildlife, especially birds and bats (Dabiri, n.d.), while wind farms don’t affect local wildlife quite as much as hydroelectric dams, it still is a concern that needs to be considered.

Solar Power

Solar power, like any renewable energy source, won’t run out of the source of its energy, unlike natural gas and coal. There is zero pollution from solar power, while it’s in operation, but creating the solar panels does take resources and electricity (Han, 2014). Solar energy, unlike other energy sources, is available in any location, allowing solar panels on places like roofs of buildings. And, according to Han in *Advantages and*

challenges with solar PV, solar technology can be modular, making expansion easier, meaning that people can put in a small amount of solar panels at one time and add on later, making it easier to complete than if it had to be all done at once. With all of this, there is a large growth potential because every roof could get a solar panel as well as many locations have potential for large scale solar farms. Even so, small scale, rooftop, solar energy is not currently affordable for everyone, as there is a large cost of installation. And, according to Han, weather and location can cause problems for solar energy, as the availability of solar radiation varies depending on location and weather, and in addition, solar power only is generated during daylight hours, making solar an unreliable source of energy. In many cases the unreliability of solar is acceptable because of the other benefits of solar energy.

Nuclear energy

One might be surprised that nuclear energy is included in the list of clean sources of energy, but nuclear energy is much cleaner than people often think. According to Richard Rhodes from Yale, in the public's eye the biggest downsides to nuclear power are risks of accidents, and exposure to nuclear waste, but nuclear energy is safer than other sources of energy. In fact, over 90% of nuclear waste can be recycled, and the nuclear waste is in "impenetrable concrete-and-steel dry casks" with its radiation slowly declining (Rhodes, 2018). And, according to Rhodes even including the large nuclear reactor incidents, nuclear energy causes less deaths than other big sources of energy.

Technically, nuclear power isn't a renewable source of energy because it requires radioactive material, but it doesn't create any greenhouse gas emissions while in operation, because the heat used to make the energy comes from a nuclear reaction instead of burning anything. One place where nuclear energy succeeds where other low-carbon energy sources don't is reliability. *Why Nuclear Power Must Be Part of the Energy Solution* says, "Nuclear power plants operate at much higher capacity factors than renewable energy sources or fossil fuels" (Rhodes, 2018), capacity factor is a measure of the percent of the time that a power plant is producing energy, so nuclear power plants are producing energy more of the time than other sources of energy. In 2016 nuclear energy plants on average had a capacity factor of 92.3%, hydroelectric was 38.2%, wind was 34.5%, and solar was only 25.1%, and coal and natural gas operated only about half the time (Rhodes, 2018), so a nuclear power plant produces energy around the clock, while all the other low-carbon sources of energy aren't producing energy most of the time. And in most scenarios there aren't many effects on the surrounding wildlife.

Research Conclusion Of the low-carbon energy sources, some are better than others. Hydropower still produces a lot of greenhouse gas emissions, it has a negative impact on the environment around it, and there aren't many more places to put hydroelectric dams, and so hydropower is not a good option for focusing resources. Wind, solar, and nuclear power don't produce any greenhouse gas emissions while in operation, and only have emissions from making the power source. Solar and wind energy only operate in the right conditions, wind needs the right wind speed, and solar

needs direct sunlight. Nuclear energy power plants are almost always operating. Solar and nuclear energy have the smallest effects on wildlife. Overall, solar and wind have similar prospects for the future, nuclear is more reliable, and its biggest drawback is negative public opinion.

CHAPTER 2

METHODOLOGY

My project was a mix of an experimental based project, and a research based project. The first portion of my project is the experimental based project, in which I was making a bicycle powered generator. After completing the experiment I shifted to research, because of the findings from my experiment.

Experiment Methodology

For the experimental portion of my capstone project my goal was to use bicycle energy as a way to generate energy. I would be asking the question, is bicycle energy a viable way to reduce energy usage in your home? To do this I planned on creating a bicycle powered generator, and charging a device on it versus charging the same device on a home power outlet. And after comparing the times, I would see if the bicycle generator was viable. The plan was that if the stationary bicycle generator was viable then I would try to make a mobile design, because then, the bicycle would be able to retain its normal usage value, and also generate electricity. But my goal at first would be to generate electricity using a stationary bicycle.

Experiment Research

I researched the use of bicycles for recreational purposes, because a stationary bicycle generator would only be useful to people using bicycles for solely recreational reasons, and while not many people use bicycles recreationally currently, the National Geographic says, “70 percent of people surveyed in the 50 biggest metro regions in the U.S. say they’re interested in biking” (Strauss, 2021). I tried to research how much energy a bicycle generator could produce, but there wasn't any information accessible which talked about the amount of power generated by a bicycle. Then I researched bicycle generators that had been done before in order to see what I needed in order to complete this project, and ideas on how to put together this type of generator. I found someone who did a similar type of bicycle generator to what I wanted. The person for *PM How to Build a Bike Generator* used a commercial bicycle trainer to make the bicycle stationary, but said making your own would work just as well (Arndt & Laughlin, 2014), so I decided to make my own out of wood, because I didn't have the money for a commercial one, and as long as the pedals spin freely there will be no difference. And I found that I would need an alternator to convert the mechanical energy into electrical energy (Alfaouri, n.d.). So, using the information I found, I bought the materials necessary for making the bicycle generator.

Building the Bicycle Generator

The first thing needed to make the bicycle generator would be a stand to make the bicycle stationary. I used spare wood to construct a stand for the back part of the bicycle, hoping that if the back was stable enough it would be unnecessary to stabilize the front. The goal was to raise the back tire off the ground and keep the bicycle upright by

the back. The back had to be raised up so that it would spin freely, in order to become stationary. After testing my first design I found that it was unsatisfactory in stabilizing the bicycle, the bicycle kept falling off. After rethinking, with the information of how the first design failed it seemed that it would work better if the front of the bike was stabilized, and to make it easier to stabilize the back it seems best to remove the back wheel, something I was originally wary of because it would make it harder to use the bicycle as normal. The second version of this contraption worked much better, the original back end stabilizer was slightly adjusted and became the front end stabilizer, it kept the bicycle from tipping left and right. And the new back end stabilizer kept the back from slipping or falling. Now that the bicycle was stabilized the next thing I had to do was attach the electronics. I put an alternator on the bicycle, the chain would spin the alternator. The alternator was wired to a car battery, and the car battery was wired to an inverter, and the inverter was connected to the power bank. In the wiring between the alternator and battery. I added diodes so that the generated energy would be stored properly in the batteries. And so the bicycle generator was built and it was ready to be tested.

Testing

To establish a baseline, to have something to compare the final results of the bicycle generator with, in order to measure how efficient the bicycle generator was, for this part I first charged the power bank on a wall outlet from zero percent. I recorded the time it took for the power bank to charge, this data was very close to how fast the charger charged while I was charging it other times, and as it took many hours to charge the power bank I only recorded the data from charging the battery once. After recording that

data, I had to use the power bank until it was back at zero percent to be ready for the next test. The next thing I did was, I recorded the data for how long it took to charge the power bank on the bicycle. After riding the bicycle for a total of two hours, it seemed like I had as much data as I was going to get.

Research Methodology

After learning about the amount of effort it takes to generate electricity I switched to finding a source of energy that is clean and efficient. First I found a source that talks about the greenhouse gas emissions by the economic sector, in order to justify the importance of finding a clean source of generating electricity. I found a source that talked about all the energy sources and said how much energy each produced and I used that to make a list of clean, or low carbon, energy sources. I then found information that talked about the advantages and disadvantages of each energy source. From the information I found, I used the most important pros and cons of the different energy sources to compare and contrast these energy sources and then make an argument as to which energy source should be focused on, in the form of research, funds, public discussion, and actual implementation.

CHAPTER 3

FINDINGS

Data from this project comes from my experiment, as well as from a couple of research sources. For the bicycle generator I hypothesized that I would produce energy less efficiently than an outlet but, I believed that charging a power bank from the bicycle generator should not take more than twice what it takes on a normal outlet. If I was right then it would take a while to charge something, but it would be worth it because I could save electricity while exercising on a regular basis for the purposes of charging a phone, or other small mobile device. After the experiment, I saw that the bicycle was way less efficient than I thought it would be.

Bicycle Graph

Riding the stationary bicycle generator was more difficult than I thought it would be, so I could not ride it for a long period of time without taking a long break in between. When I started pedaling I checked the multimeter reading and saw that there was a very small amount of voltage, but after rechecking making sure everything was connected properly, I continued pedaling. At this point I already knew the efficiency wouldn't be what I had hoped. I continued testing hoping the efficiency of the bicycle energy, though not being great, would be enough that it would be something that would be viable to use outside of the experiment. After one hour the bicycle power had charged the power bank only two percent, the same amount of time it took the house outlet to charge the power bank to eleven percent. In two hours on the bicycle I got the power bank to five percent, the same amount of time it took the house outlet to charge it to 26 percent. I then

calculated out how many hours that would mean it would take to charge the power bank completely. With it seeming to charge at a mostly consistent rate so far it looked like to charge the power bank to fully charge the power bank on the bicycle would take 40 hours, while fully charging on the house outlet only took eight hours. So I compared the sets of data that I recorded for fully charging the power bank from the wall and the bicycle, and compiled it into a bar graph. From this data I found that bicycle powered energy is much too inefficient to be viable.

Figure 1. *Time to charge power bank vs. Energy source*

Research Graphs

I found a couple important graphs for my project through research. They were found online, and relate to the energy source comparison research portion of my project.

Emissions by Sector Graph

In an article entitled *Sources of Greenhouse Gas Emissions* from the EPA the greenhouse gas emissions are compared by economic sectors. This graph shows that

electric power accounts for 25% of total greenhouse gas emissions, making it the second largest greenhouse gas emitter. With number one being only three percentage points larger than the energy sector.

Figure 2. *Total U.S. greenhouse gas emissions by economic sector* (EPA, 2015)

Energy Source Comparison Graph

In an article titled *What are the safest and cleanest sources of energy*, by Ritchie, Hanna, there is a very informative graph that compares energy sources by how much greenhouse gasses they produce, how many deaths they have caused, and how much they are used globally. In this graph it shows coal as producing 820 tonnes of greenhouse gas per gigawatt hour (GWh), one gigawatt hour is roughly equivalent to the amount of energy 150 people use in a year. Natural gas produces 490 tonnes per GWh. Hydropower produces 34 tonnes per GWh, wind produces 4 tonnes, solar 5 tonnes, and nuclear power actually produces only 3 tonnes of greenhouse gas emissions per GWh, less than solar and wind. As far as safety, coal has about 24.6 deaths per terawatt hour (TWh), which is about as much as 150,000 people use in a year. Natural gas causes 2.8 deaths per TWh,

hydropower 1.3, wind 0.04, solar 0.02, and nuclear causes only 0.03 deaths per TWh, including the Chernobyl and Fukushima disasters.

Figure 3. *What are the safest and cleanest energy source* (Ritchie, 2020)

CHAPTER 4

CONCLUSIONS

This project was a quest to find clean energy. First there was an experiment to see if people could generate their own electricity, using a bicycle. Then, after concluding that the bicycle generator wouldn't work very well to be used regularly, the quest turned toward the prominent low-carbon energy sources to find which is the most efficient. From experiment data, a bicycle powered generator was too inefficient to be viable. When used within a daily schedule, it would take a week to get to a power bank five percent. This makes use of the bicycle generator impractical and unviable, but it shows how difficult it is to produce electricity, and it makes finding a clean source of energy seem more important. And so the question becomes, what source of clean energy is most viable? In terms of environmental impact and efficiency. This is an important question because electricity uses a quarter of greenhouse gasses. The main sources of low-carbon energy are hydroelectric, solar, wind and nuclear. Hydroelectric power still produces greenhouse gas emissions, more than any of the other sources looked at in this research, through the plants it floods. It also can be very harmful to local wildlife because of the creation of the reservoir, and it has a small amount of growth potential. Therefore, hydroelectric power is not a good option on which to focus resources. Wind and solar energy are very similar, they both have little effect on surrounding wildlife, produce no emissions while in operation, and have lots of growth potential, but they both also require

certain conditions in order to work so do not operate much of the time. They are different, though, in that wind turbines are huge and loud making it so they cannot be used within cities, or on residential property, whereas solar is modular and silent making it possible to install on any roof, in every city. Nuclear energy is not renewable in the same way that the previously mentioned energy sources are, but it produces less emissions, it is equally safe, and it is way more efficient than any of the mentioned sources, in fact it is more efficient than the main, non-renewable, sources of energy. The biggest draw back for nuclear energy is public opinion that nuclear energy is unsafe. So, hydropower is helpful as it is, but should not have additional resources allocated to it. Wind's growth is good, but other sources are still better to focus on. Solar is really helpful and resources should be put into getting it on to more roofs. But, nuclear energy could be doing a lot to shift away from high-carbon energy sources, nuclear energy needs more resources to be put into researching it and building more nuclear power plants, because the big problems that cause wind and solar to remain minority energy producers, don't affect nuclear, meaning it could provide a much larger portion of the electricity. So if the question is: what is the best source of energy to focus resources on, in terms of the energy sources' emissions and efficiency? Wind and Solar are good to care about, but nuclear is best to focus on.

ANNOTATED BIBLIOGRAPHY

Arndt, R. Z., & Laughlin, P. (2014, March 24). *Pedal Power! How to Build a Bike Generator*. Popular Mechanics.

<https://www.popularmechanics.com/technology/gadgets/how-to/a10245/pedal-power-how-to-build-a-bike-generator-16627209/>

This Article is about how one person built a bicycle powered generator. This person used a commercial bicycle trainer, which is something you put a bike onto to make it stationary, and removed the resistance so that the rear wheel could spin freely. They then attached the wheel to an inverter using a chain on the opposite side of the wheel as the normal chain to use the bike. To prevent power from flowing the wrong way a diode was used, a diode directs current in only one direction. The power they produced was not enough to be used regularly, but if stored in batteries it could be saved for backup power during an outage.

The article is helpful because it shows one way to make a stationary bicycle power generator. I had not known about diodes, that is something I plan to research further. I already knew that bicycle trainers exist for purchase, but I will look into that further. The idea to store multiple batteries and use it for a power outage is a really good idea that I may decide to use in the future.

Dabiri, J. (n.d.). *Wind energy facts, advantages, and disadvantages*. Caltech Science Exchange.

<https://scienceexchange.caltech.edu/topics/sustainability/wind-energy-advantages-disadvantages>

This source talks about the advantages and disadvantages of wind power, as well as some general facts about wind turbines. The source says that wind turbines are about 250 feet tall, and wind farms are remote, but still easily connected to the grid. Smaller turbines can be used for power locally, the smaller turbines average about 100 feet tall, and produce much less energy. The source said that wind energy has been growing, and wind turbine prices have been decreasing. The source said that extreme winds are a problem to wind turbines, because “a strong gale contains 1,000 times more power than a light breeze” and engineers haven’t found a way to capture such a large range of input. And, the source says, “turbines may be overbuilt to withstand winds they will not experience at many sites, driving up costs and material use.” The source also says that wind farms affect wildlife, it mostly harms birds and bats. The source also says that “The construction and maintenance of wind farms involves energy-intensive activities such as trucking, road-building, concrete production, and steel construction.” And that turbine blades are not easily recyclable.

This source is helpful because it talks about one of the sources of energy that I am comparing. It talks about important drawbacks for using wind energy. The information

about not being able to pick up the very variable wind is helpful. It is important to know about the environmental impacts of wind power that this talks about, the harm it does to wildlife is very important information for my research. And it is important to know about what it takes to make and maintain the wind farm. Overall this source is important to compare wind energy to other energy sources.

Electric Generator: A basic introduction to how generators work, their features and applications. (2019, May 15). The Economic Times.

<https://economictimes.indiatimes.com/small-biz/productline/power-generation/electric-generator-an-basic-introduction-to-how-generators-work-their-features-and-applications/articleshow/69343338.cms?from=mdr>

Generators use magnetic fields to generate electricity. In generators a copper coil (which is a conductor) is wrapped around a metal core. This is rotated between the poles of a magnet. There is some kind of mechanical energy, which rotates the coil and its core. When the coil rotates it cuts the magnetic field between the magnets, the magnetic field interferes with the electrons in the conductor, causing an electric current to flow inside of it.

This source is helpful because it better helps me understand how generators work in general. Many other sources that I didn't use only talked about specific generators. As I want to find a generator able to be attached to a bike, I need to know how generators work so I know how I can generate electricity.

EPA. (2022, August 5). *Sources of Greenhouse Gas Emissions* | US EPA. Environmental Protection Agency. Retrieved April 11, 2023, from <https://www.epa.gov/ghgemissions/sources-greenhouse-gas-emissions>

This source gives information about greenhouse gas emissions used by different economic sectors. It gives data in percentages detailing how much energy each sector uses. It gives the trends of greenhouse gas emissions from 1990 to 2020. The source gives some further details on the greenhouse gas emissions by the electric power sector. And the source gives information on trends in greenhouse emissions by the electric sector from 1990 to 2020. It then talks about a few ways to reduce emissions from the electric power production. The source then goes into similar detail for the other economic sectors.

This source is important, mostly because of the data about how much greenhouse gas emissions each economic sector uses, because that information shows the importance of using a clean source of energy. According to this source energy is the second highest sector, producing a quarter of our emissions, so reducing emissions in the energy sector would be very helpful to the whole. The information it gives on ways to reduce emissions may be helpful, I may talk about the solutions it talks about in my writing. The largest importance of this source is that it shows the importance of my project.

Fendt, L., & Parsons, J. (2021, March 2). *Why aren't we looking at more hydropower?*

MIT Climate Portal.

<https://climate.mit.edu/ask-mit/why-arent-we-looking-more-hydropower>

This source is talking about hydropower. It starts off by saying that worldwide hydropower is the largest “low-carbon energy source.” And it talks about how much energy it is used to produce, compared to other renewable energy sources. But then the source shifts to talking about the drawbacks of hydroelectric power. The source says that “Hydro plants need a consistent supply of water and a large amount of land” meaning that there is a limited amount of locations for a hydropower dam. The source goes on to explain that the building of a dam can cause problems, because a dam requires a large reservoir to work and creating that reservoir floods plants and other organic matter. And “This material decays over time, releasing greenhouse gases” and this greenhouse gas emissions is highly variable. And the source says that many countries, including the U.S. “have already built out most of their suitable hydro resources” meaning that there isn’t a whole lot of growing potential for the hydroelectric power industry. The source goes on to explain that “Reservoirs drastically change the landscape and rivers they are built on” and this change of landscape negatively impacts wildlife around the dam. And these dams have forced humans to relocate as well, because of flooding, and changes in water levels caused by the dams.

This source is helpful to my project because I am comparing the main sources of clean energy and then dividing and arguing which energy source is best. It seems that this article is basically saying that hydroelectric power is good where it is, but it doesn’t have much growing potential. This makes it not a good choice of energy to focus our attention

on, because to make an impact in the emissions of making energy there needs to be significant growing potential. And it seems as though the amount of greenhouse gas emissions still produced through this form of electricity production makes it not the optimal choice.

Granath, E. (2020, February 26). *What is a diode and what is it used for?* Power & Beyond.

<https://www.power-and-beyond.com/what-is-a-diode-and-what-is-it-used-for-a-908189/>

This source talks about what a diode is. A diode forces electricity to flow in one direction and not the other. A diode can turn ac into dc, isolate signals from a supply and mix signals. One side of a diode is positive and the other side is negative. LEDs work by photons being emitted when electrons cross the diode. The most common application of a diode is converting ac into dc. Diodes are able to make electricity flow in only one direction because they have a built in electric field.

This source is helpful because it explains why people use diodes in making bicycle generators. It is very good to know why a diode is important and how it does what it does. I wouldn't have realized that there are multiple types of diode if I hadn't read this source. And the connection to LEDs help me understand their usefulness. But mostly it just shows why the diode is used, and why I should use it in my project.

Han, A. (2014, April). *Advantages and challenges with solar PV – Solar photovoltaic*. Sites at Lafayette.

<https://sites.lafayette.edu/egrs352-sp14-pv/technology/advantages-and-challenges-with-solar-pv/>

The source talks about advantages and disadvantages of solar power. The source says that solar power, like any renewable energy source, won't run out of the source of its energy, unlike natural gas and coal. The source says that there is zero pollution from solar power, while it's in operation, but creating the solar panels does take resources and electricity. The source says that solar energy is available in any location, allowing solar panels on places like roofs of buildings. The source says that solar technology can be modular, making expansion easier. The source says that solar energy is not currently affordable for everyone. The source talks about how weather and location can cause problems for solar energy, as the availability of solar radiation varies depending on location and weather, and in addition solar power only is generated during daylight hours.

This source is important because it talks about pros and cons of solar power. It is important to talk about the variability, and therefore unreliability of solar panels. And how location, weather, and time of day can all impede the operation of solar panels. It is also very important to include in my paper the fact that solar panels are able to be included in existing buildings. The fact that solar (and wind) aren't going to run out of

the source of their energy is seemingly obvious, but still important to talk about. Overall, this source is important to help me compare solar power to other types of power.

How Many Watts Does A Laptop Use? [Actual Usage & Costs Revealed - 1084 Studied].

(2022, August 24). Eco Cost Savings.

<https://ecocostsavings.com/how-many-watts-does-a-laptop-use/>

This source is about laptop energy consumption. Most laptops consume about 65 watts of electricity. An average laptop under average conditions uses 55.45 watt hours a day, and 20.24 kilowatt hours a year. But this is assuming less than an hour of computer being active a day, adjusting to an hour and a half of laptop use with the average laptop changes the watt hours to 325 a day and 97,500 watt hours a year or 9,750 kilowatt hours a year. Laptops consume relatively little energy.

This source is helpful because I may try to power a laptop using the bike generator I end up making. Knowing the energy output of average laptops is important because I want to know how much energy I would need to power a laptop, and if powering laptops by bike power would make any significant difference. I don't know how much energy the bike can generate right now, but I hope it can do more than just powering a laptop, because it seems like that may not be that much of a big deal from what this says about how much a laptop consumes.

Nyberg, M. (n.d.). *2021 Total System Electric Generation*. California Energy Commission.

<https://www.energy.ca.gov/data-reports/energy-almanac/california-electricity-data/2021-total-system-electric-generation>

This source gives a lot of useful data about California electricity generation. It gives the sources of energy California uses and the amount of electricity generated in Gigawatts hours (GWh) and percent, total imports of that energy in GWh and percent and it gives the Total California Power Mix in GWh and percent. It then summarizes the data, and gives a variety of different graphs using pieces of the data.

This source is useful for my project because as I'm talking about types of energy, and their efficiency, it is important to know exactly how much energy we use from different sources. Especially knowing the percentages of each type of energy used in California is helpful information to my topic. And if I'm going to argue that something needs to be changed, I better know the starting point.

Opez, S. (n.d.). *How to Build a Bicycle Generator : 9 Steps*.

<https://www.instructables.com/How-To-Build-A-Bicycle-Generator/>

This source gives clear step-by-step instructions on how to build a bicycle powered generator. The bicycle is put on a stand, with the back wheel raised. The tire is taken off the wheel and is connected to a motor with a drive belt. The motor is wired to a battery,

with a diode making the electricity only flow into the battery. Then the battery is connected to an inverter.

This source is helpful because it gives a really good explanation of what to do in order to make a bicycle generator. This source also clearly lists the resources needed to repeat what they did. Knowing one way that this has been done with a stationary bike is really helpful in formulating a way I can do a similar thing. I do not like that whoever wrote this article had to take off the tire to make the bike a generator, because I want my bicycle to still be usable to bring me somewhere.

Rhodes, R. (2018, July 19). *Why Nuclear Power Must Be Part of the Energy Solution*.

Yale E360.

<https://e360.yale.edu/features/why-nuclear-power-must-be-part-of-the-energy-solution-environmentalists-climate>

This source talks about nuclear energy, including some of the advantages and disadvantages of it. The source claims that the environmentalists' condemnation of nuclear power is misplaced. It says that since the power plant uses nuclear fission to generate heat, it doesn't produce greenhouse gas emissions. The only greenhouse gas emissions come from creating the power plant, and is comparable to solar power. The source then talks about how nuclear energy is usable around the clock, it reliably produces energy in most circumstances, whereas other low carbon energies produce energy intermittently. In 2016 nuclear energy plants operated at full power on average of

92.3%, hydroelectric was 38.2%, wind was 34.5%, and solar was only 25.1%, and coal and natural gas operate only about half the time. The source says that nuclear releases less radiation into the environment than other major energy sources. The source says that in the public's eye the biggest downsides to nuclear power is risk of accidents, and exposure to nuclear waste. The source argues that even including these incidents, nuclear energy is safer than other sources of energy. And the source says that there isn't as much nuclear waste as thought, over 90% of nuclear waste can be recycled, and the nuclear waste radiation is slowly declining. The source ends with "Nuclear power is not the only answer to the world-scale threat of global warming. Renewables have their place" and, the source says that nuclear energy is "a valuable, even an irreplaceable, part of the solution to the greatest energy threat in the history of humankind."

This source is very important to my project because it gives a lot of really good information about nuclear power. The information about greenhouse gas emissions from nuclear energy being equatable to solar is very important to talk about when comparing and contrasting different power sources. The reliability of nuclear power is very important to talk about as most low carbon energy sources are very unreliable compared to natural gas and coal, but nuclear power is more reliable than these sources. And it is very important for my research that the source talks about the misconceptions the public has about nuclear energy being dangerous. Overall this is very important for my final

paper as it helps me to talk about nuclear energy and compare it to other sources of energy.

Ritchie, H. (2020, February 10). *What are the safest and cleanest sources of energy?* Our World in Data. Retrieved April 8, 2023, from <https://ourworldindata.org/safest-sources-of-energy>

This source offers data on clean and safe sources of energy. The source gives data on the tonnes of greenhouse gasses per gigawatt-hour a type of energy produces. It tells how many deaths each produce per terawatt-hour, and it gives a percentage of global energy generation for each energy source. The source then goes on to explain how deaths included in the data include air pollution and accidents in the supply chain. And it talks about how you don't need to go into the long term to see the benefits of switching away from coal and fossil fuels because the death rates for those are so much higher than the death rates of energies that are better for the environment.

This source is important for my project, because the data is very applicable to my topic. The amount of greenhouse gasses produced by each energy is very important because this project is about finding a clean source of energy. And the safety of a source of energy is very important in getting it implemented in any populated area. This gives a really great basis for finding the best source of energy to rely on, because it gives the data on which energy sources pollute and which energy sources are safe.

Schmitz, H. (2021, October 13). *An Introductory Guide to Hand-Crank Generators*.

ThisGenerator.com. Retrieved August 18, 2022, from

<https://thisgenerator.com/an-introductory-guide-to-hand-crank-generators/>

According to the article, hand crank generators use dynamos to produce energy. A dynamo uses mechanical energy into electrical energy. In the dynamo there are two stationary magnets, and in between them is a coil, when the coil is rotated, it experiences a changing magnetic field. The changing magnetic field creates an electric current within the coil. The coil is rotated by the hand crank. A hand crank generator doesn't produce much energy.

This source is helpful because I plan on creating energy using the rotation from the bike's wheel. This helps me to get an understanding of what a simple generator does to produce energy. A hand crank has much in common with what I want for my bike powered generator. It is relatively small, it is very portable, and it uses human power instead of gas like many other generators.

Strauss, I. (2021, September 21). *Is the U.S. becoming more bike friendly?* National Geographic.

<https://www.nationalgeographic.com/environment/article/is-the-us-becoming-more-bike-friendly>

This source talks about sentiment in the U.S. toward bicycles, and how it has been increasing. Because of the pandemic more people have been riding their bicycles. Transportation is the largest source of emissions, so with more people focusing on climate change more people focus on transportation with less emissions, such as bicycling. Overall the U.S. is not very friendly to bicyclists, currently there are very few safe bicycle roads/lanes. But, even before the pandemic the U.S. has been making efforts to improve bicycle networks, “Between 1991 and 2021, there was a six-fold increase in paved, off-road trails, from 5,904 miles to 39,329 miles” (Straus). Rural towns may be decreasing in bicycle usage, but cities are increasing in bicycle usage.

This source is useful because it shows how bicycles are important. It shows that people, especially in cities, are increasingly using bikes, which is important if my topic relies on people using bikes. It also shows that more safe bike trails are being made, meaning the amount of people biking will increase. Overall, this source basically validates my bicycle project as something that could affect many Americans across the USA.